

Redox-active Chiroptical Switching in Mono- and Bis-Iron-Ethynyl-Carbo[6]Helicenes Studied by Electronic and Vibrational Circular Dichroism and Resonance Raman Optical Activity

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Figure 39. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 480 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Figure 40. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 490 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Figure 41. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 500 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Figure 42. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 510 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Figure 43. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 520 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Figure 44. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 530 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Figure 45. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 532 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Figure 46. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 540 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Figure 47. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 550 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Figure 48. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 560 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Figure 49. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 570 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Figure 50. Experimental (top, offset, 532 nm incident wavelength) and calculated (bottom, 580 nm incident wavelength) RROA spectrum for *M-2a*. The calculated vibrational frequencies were scaled by a factor of 0.95.

Detailed analysis of the RROA intensity of the alkynyl stretching mode

Table S11. $\beta(G')_p^2$ and $\beta(A)_p^2$ for the alkynyl stretching mode.

Wavelength / nm	$\beta(G')_p^2 / \text{\AA}^4\text{amu}^{-1}$	$\beta(A)_p^2 / \text{\AA}^4\text{amu}^{-1}$
490	1'395'630.49	1'180.95
500	1'464'928.37	8'098.61
510	1'496'827.31	13'355.99
520	1'493'484.73	17'330.26
530	1'471'169.53	20'987.93
540	1'421'256.05	23'224.34
550	1'354'619.36	24'325.42
560	1'276'197.96	24'574.64
570	1'193'420.07	24'185.30
580	1'119'294.97	24'133.97

Further inspection of the data for $\beta(G')^2$ showed that the imaginary part of the property tensors dominates the overall intensity, since the imaginary part of the electric dipole-electric dipole polarizability transition tensor turned out to be several orders of magnitude larger than the other transition tensors. Hence, the analysis carried out in the original publication does not properly attribute the ROA intensity to the individual property tensors. However, for the sake of completeness, we provide the corrected raw data below.

Table S12. Electric dipole-magnetic dipole polarizability tensor G' as a function of two different alkynyl bond lengths for an incident laser wavelength of 490 nm.

Tensor Element	Alkynyl Bond Length / pm	
	136	111
XX	-7.53	-2.63
XY	0.57	10.68
XZ	-66.91	-67.60
YX	15.68	18.70
YY	-40.55	-41.04
YZ	18.50	12.06
ZX	-27.06	-30.57
ZY	-89.26	-90.27
ZZ	56.89	61.11

Table S13. Electric dipole-magnetic dipole polarizability tensor G' as a function of two different alkynyl bond lengths for an incident laser wavelength of 530 nm.

Tensor Element	Alkynyl Bond Length / pm	
	136	111
XX	0.12	0.45
XY	17.33	15.71
XZ	-71.24	-64.10
YX	14.13	16.68
YY	-37.45	-37.89
YZ	15.78	10.01
ZX	-22.81	-26.02
ZY	-81.74	-81.48
ZZ	52.32	55.44

Table S14. Electric dipole-magnetic dipole polarizability tensor G' as a function of two different alkynyl bond lengths for an incident laser wavelength of 540 nm.

Tensor Element	Alkynyl Bond Length / pm	
	136	111
XX	1.51	0.82
XY	20.00	16.00
XZ	-71.56	-62.89
YX	13.87	16.25
YY	-36.72	-37.13
YZ	15.22	9.61
ZX	-21.98	-25.10
ZY	-80.06	-79.31
ZZ	51.30	54.14

Table S15. Electric dipole-magnetic dipole polarizability tensor G' as a function of two different alkynyl bond lengths for an incident laser wavelength of 580 nm.

Tensor Element	Alkynyl Bond Length / pm	
	136.00	111.00
XX	4.72	1.33
XY	25.23	15.34
XZ	-70.03	-57.74
YX	13.05	14.79
YY	-34.01	-34.38
YZ	13.19	8.21
ZX	-19.39	-22.17
ZY	-73.11	-70.76
ZZ	47.40	49.40

Table S16. Electric dipole-electric dipole polarizability tensor α as a function of two different alkynyl bond lengths for an incident laser wavelength of 490 nm.

Tensor Element	Alkynyl Bond Length / pm	
	136.00	111.00
XX	1'104.94	1'052.69
XY	-54.62	-70.38
XZ	128.77	99.64
YX	-54.62	-70.38
YY	843.21	834.33
YZ	37.59	33.22
ZX	128.77	99.64
ZY	37.59	33.22
ZZ	734.14	726.14

Table S17. Electric dipole-electric dipole polarizability tensor α as a function of two different alkynyl bond lengths for an incident laser wavelength of 530 nm.

Tensor Element	Alkynyl Bond Length / pm	
	136.00	111.00
XX	1'126.79	1'044.17
XY	-52.43	-67.83
XZ	122.87	95.00
YX	-52.43	-67.83
YY	831.88	823.01
YZ	37.35	32.99
ZX	122.87	95.00
ZY	37.35	32.99
ZZ	723.03	714.35

Table S18. Electric dipole-electric dipole polarizability tensor α as a function of two different alkynyl bond lengths for an incident laser wavelength of 540 nm.

Tensor Element	Alkynyl Bond Length / pm	
	136.00	111.00
XX	1'128.97	1'040.80
XY	-51.99	-67.25
XZ	121.48	94.21
YX	-51.99	-67.25
YY	829.44	820.59
YZ	37.26	32.89
ZX	121.48	94.21
ZY	37.26	32.89
ZZ	720.71	711.81

Table S19. Electric dipole-electric dipole polarizability tensor α as a function of two different alkynyl bond lengths for an incident laser wavelength of 580 nm.

Tensor Element	Alkynyl Bond Length / pm	
	136.00	111.00
XX	1'126.31	1'025.99
XY	-50.61	-65.20
XZ	116.87	91.97
YX	-50.61	-65.20
YY	820.97	812.26
YZ	36.79	32.39
ZX	116.87	91.97
ZY	36.79	32.39
ZZ	712.55	703.12

Figure 51. xx element of the electric dipole-magnetic dipole polarizability tensor G' , as a function of the alkynyl bond length for different wavelengths of the incident laser beam. Note that for each wavelength, G' has only been calculate for two bond lengths (111 pm and 136 pm); the dashed lines are not intended to imply a linear relationship but only to help visualizing the trend.

Figure 52. xx element of the electric dipole-dipole polarizability tensor α , as a function of the alkynyl bond length for different wavelengths of the incident laser beam. Note that for each wavelength, α has only been calculate for two bond lengths (111 pm and 136 pm); the dashed lines are not intended to imply a linear relationship but only to help visualizing the trend.